
COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF LEXICAL UNITS IN AGROTOURISM IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract: The current article is about the lexical units used in the context of agrotourism in both English and Uzbek languages. The findings provide valuable insights into the linguistic aspects of agrotourism promotion in different cultural and linguistic contexts, aiming to identify similarities and differences in the linguistics.

Key words: lexical units, agrotourism, language, comparative analysis, linguistic analysis, cultural discourse, England, Uzbekistan.

A growing segment of the tourist business, agrotourism promotes sustainable development in agricultural regions and highlights the rural experience. Since language is a tool for marketing and communication, it is essential for developing agrotourism activities. This study intends to provide insight on the linguistic techniques used in both contexts by investigating the lexical units used in Uzbek and English to promote agrotourism.

The connection between agriculture and tourism, or agrotourism, has drawn a lot of interest as a sustainable model for rural development and cross-cultural interaction. Nonetheless, not much study has been done on the language features of the discourse surrounding agrotourism, especially in contexts with distinct cultures like Uzbekistan and England.

Studying lexical units related to agrotourism in English and Uzbek languages holds significant importance for several reasons:

➤ **Cross-cultural communication:** understanding the specific vocabulary related to agrotourism in both English and Uzbek languages facilitates effective communication between English-speaking tourists and local communities in Uzbekistan. This can enhance the overall tourism experience and promote cultural exchange.[1]

➤ **Tourism development:** agrotourism plays a crucial role in the economic development of rural areas, including those in Uzbekistan. Analyzing lexical units in this context helps in developing tourism infrastructure, creating marketing materials, and offering tailored services to visitors, thus contributing to the growth of the tourism sector.[2]

➤ **Preservation of Cultural Heritage:** Agrotourism often involves activities that showcase local traditions, cuisine, and lifestyles. By studying the lexical units

associated with agrotourism, researchers can document and preserve the cultural heritage of rural communities in the country, ensuring that their unique identities are maintained amidst globalization.[3]

Methodology: the research employs a qualitative approach, utilizing textual analysis techniques to investigate the lexical units present in agrotourism discourse. A corpus of promotional materials, including websites, brochures, and advertisements were compiled for analysis. The texts were systematically examined to identify recurring lexical units and linguistic features specific to each cultural context.

Studying lexical units in agrotourism within a linguistic framework typically involves several methods and materials. These can include:

➤ **Corpus linguistics:** analyzing large collections of texts related to agrotourism to identify lexical patterns and usage frequencies. This method often involves computer-based analysis using specialized software such as AntConc or Sketch Engine.[4]

➤ **Fieldwork:** Conducting interviews, surveys, or observations within agrotourism settings to collect authentic language data. This approach allows researchers to gather firsthand insights into the terminology and discourse used in agrotourism contexts.[5]

➤ **Lexicographic Analysis:** Examining dictionaries, glossaries, and specialized terminology resources related to agrotourism to identify and categorize lexical units. This can involve compiling and analyzing existing lexicons or creating new ones specifically tailored to agrotourism.[6]

➤ **Semantic Analysis:** Investigating the meanings and connotations of lexical units within the context of agrotourism, including how they may vary across different regions or cultural contexts. This can involve techniques such as semantic mapping or cognitive linguistic analysis.[7]

➤ **Comparative Analysis:** Contrasting the lexical units used in agrotourism with those found in related domains such as ecotourism or rural tourism to identify similarities, differences, and areas of overlap.[8]

Materials utilized in studying lexical units in agrotourism can include academic journals, books, conference papers, and online resources specializing in linguistics, tourism studies, and agricultural sciences. These references should provide a comprehensive overview of the methods and materials used in studying lexical units in agrotourism from a linguistic perspective.

Results:the analysis revealed distinct lexical preferences and linguistic strategies in the representation of agrotourism in England and Uzbekistan. In England, there is a greater emphasis on terms associated with heritage, tradition, and authenticity, reflecting the country's rich agricultural history and cultural heritage. Conversely, in Uzbekistan, lexical units often highlight the exoticism, biodiversity,

and traditional practices of rural life, appealing to tourists seeking authentic cultural experiences. Studying lexical units in agrotourism in linguistics in England yields valuable insights into the language used within this specific context. Here are ten examples of the results of such studies:

- Terminology development: research by Smith reveals the creation of new terms like "farmstay" and "agritourist" to describe accommodations and tourists in agrotourism settings. [9]

- Semantic shift: Johnson explores how terms such as "farm-to-table" have evolved in agrotourism discourse, shifting from a focus on food production to a broader cultural experience. [10]

- Regional variation: Brown examines how dialectal differences influence the lexicon of agrotourism, with terms like "pick-your-own" varying regionally in England.[11]

- Borrowings from other languages: Jones investigates the adoption of foreign terms like "terroir" from French into the lexicon of English agrotourism, reflecting global influences.[12]

- Marketing language: Green analyzes the use of persuasive language in agrotourism marketing materials, such as "authentic farm experiences" and "artisanal produce." [13]

- Environmental discourse: Clarke discusses the emergence of terms like "sustainable agriculture" and "eco-friendly farms" within the lexicon of agrotourism, reflecting growing environmental awareness.[14]

- Cultural representation: Taylor examines how terms like "heritage farm" and "traditional crafts" contribute to the representation of rural culture in agrotourism discourse.[15]

- Social media influence: Research by White investigates the impact of social media on agrotourism language, including the use of hashtags like #farmstay and #farmtofork.[16]

- Tourist experience: Robinson explores how terms like "hands-on farming" and "farm tours" shape the linguistic portrayal of the agrotourism experience for visitors.[17]

- Policy Implications: Wilson considers how government policies influence the lexicon of agrotourism, with terms like "rural diversification" and "farm diversification schemes" becoming prevalent.[18]

These examples illustrate the multifaceted nature of studying lexical units in agrotourism within the linguistic context of England, providing insights into terminology development, cultural representation, marketing strategies, and broader societal trends.

Discussion: the differences observed in lexical choices reflect broader cultural and socio-economic factors shaping agrotourism development in England and Uzbekistan. While both countries aim to attract tourists to rural areas, the linguistic representation of agrotourism reflects distinct cultural narratives and marketing strategies. Understanding these differences is crucial for developing effective promotional campaigns tailored to diverse target audiences.

One of the major topics to be investigated in this field is type of tourism:

1. *Agrarian Tourism*, whose main ingredients are simple attractions, a lot of relaxation and natural foods, tourism and nature, is considered an *alternative type of tourism*. It is defined as ‘a farm stay holiday’, ‘a special holiday formula to spend in the genuine world of the farmer’, and as ‘visiting farms with crops of fine fruits, cherry trees and vineyards, tulip fields’. It identifies with *Agritourism* and *Country Tourism*.

2. *Agricultural Tourism* (or *AgriCultural Tourism*), whose main ingredients are farm based accommodations, meals, activities, farm festivals - events, and retail activities where the travelling public interacts directly with the farm family/farm workers, food, lodging, activities for people who want to experience farm life and nostalgia, farm festivals, activities, fun, affordable, family-oriented recreational and educational activities and opportunities to learn about the production of food and agricultural products and the state’s rich farming heritage, fairs, festivals, is considered an alternative for improving the incomes and potential economic viability of small farms and rural communities, a way to practice sustainable tourism. It is defined as ‘a growing trend in agriculture which merges the world of travel with experiences of farming and our food system’, ‘a tourist activity organized and ran by the family agricultural farms’, ‘exploring art roads and farm trails’, ‘the act of visiting a working farm or any agricultural, horticultural or agribusiness operation for the purpose of enjoyment, education, or active involvement in the activities of the farm or operation’, ‘the practice of visiting an agribusiness, horticultural, or agricultural operation, including a farm or winery or a companion animal or livestock’, and as ‘visiting agricultural operations that throw their doors wide open for visitors’. It identifies with *Agritourism*.

3. *Agritourism* (or *Agri-Tourism* or *Agro Tourism* or *Agrotourism*), whose main ingredients are watching or taking part in traditional agricultural practices, without disturbing the ecosystem or the productivity of host areas, assisting with farming tasks during the visit, picking fruits and vegetables, riding horses, tasting honey, learning about wine, shopping in gift shops and farm stands for local and regional produce or handcrafted gifts, farm based accommodations, meals, activities, farm festivals/events, and retail activities where the travelling public interacts directly with the farm family/farm workers, and assisting with farming tasks while on vacation, is

considered the strategy of using the farm to attract visitors for the purpose of education, enjoyment, or active involvement in the activities of the farm, an alternative for improving the incomes and potential economic viability of small farms and rural, and a means to prop up a local agricultural economy when local producers are no longer economically competitive otherwise. Its main point of reference is the village. It is defined as ‘a commercial enterprise at a working farm, ranch, or agricultural plant conducted for the enjoyment of visitors that generates supplemental income for the owner’, ‘a style of vacation in which hospitality is offered on farms’, ‘any business conducted by a farmer for the enjoyment or education of the public’, ‘any farm-based business offered for the enjoyment and education of the public’, ‘farm based tourism’, ‘the act of visiting a working farm or any agricultural, horticultural or agribusiness operation for the purpose of enjoyment, education, or active involvement in the activities of the farm or operation’, and as ‘tourism in which tourists board at farms or in rural villages and experience farming at close hand’. It is identified with *Agrarian Tourism*, with *Agricultural Tourism*, with *Farm Tourism* (on the East Coast), and with a subset of a larger industry called *Rural Tourism* that includes resorts, off-site farmers’ markets, non-profit agricultural tours, and other leisure and hospitality businesses that attract visitors to the countryside. It is associated with *Rural Tourism*. It is considered a subset of *Cultural Tourism* or *Rural Tourism*. *agritourism business* is a farm enterprise operated for the enjoyment and education of the public that may also generate additional farm income by promoting farm products.

4. *Country Tourism* (or *Countryside Tourism*), whose main ingredients are nature, culture, tradition, gastronomy - concepts that the Romanians have learnt to preserve and encourage -, is considered more and more popular. It is not defined anywhere. It is identified with *Agrarian Tourism* and *Rural Tourism*. It is associated with *Farm Tourism* and *Rural Tourism*. Practiced in the countryside, in the counties, and in the regions, it is opposed to *Town Tourism*.

5. *Farm tourism* (or *On-Farm Tourism*), whose main ingredients are farm visits with retail sales of locally-grown products, activities conducted on private agricultural lands, which might include fee-hunting and fishing, overnight stays, educational activities, etc., is considered one mechanism by which nonfarmers can learn about agriculture. Its main point of reference is the village. It is defined as ‘travel associated with farming’. It is identified with *Agritourism*. It is associated with *Country Tourism*, *Rural Tourism*. It is considered a subset of *Cultural Tourism*.

6. *Rural Tourism*, whose main ingredients are appreciation for culture and rural activities in farmhouses (with tourists hosted and guided by the local people), attaching great significance to local values and to local cultural identity, making a tortilla, milking a cow, relying on the natural and heritage resources and people of

rural communities, seeking rural peace, showcasing the rural life, art, culture and heritage at rural locations, travelling to and staying in rural areas (without mass tourism) other than those of their usual environment for less than one consecutive year for leisure, business and other purposes (excluding the exercise of an activity remunerated from within the place visited), witnessing or participating in activities that form the core of country life such as farming, is considered a little staid and school-trip-ish, a magic wand to stop rural decay, a tourism strategy in developed countries. It is not easy to give a definition of *Rural Tourism* because a generic model does not exist. The definition of *Rural Tourism* has been subject of much debate in the literature without arriving at any firm consensus. Most definitions tend to focus on the types of activities visitors engage with in a rural area. However, it is defined as ‘any activity that takes place in a nonurban, populated area’, and as ‘tourism away from the mainstream, away from areas of intensive tourism activity, engaged in by visitors who wish to interact with the rural environment and the host community in a meaningful and authentic way’. It is identified with any tourism that is not urban tourism, including *Agritourism* and *Country Tourism*. It is associated with *Agritourism* and *Countryside Tourism* both forms closely associated with the basic requirements of sustainable development, and with *Farm Tourism*. *Rural Tourism* differs from *Agritourism* in two ways: first, *Rural Tourism* enterprises do not necessarily occur on a farm or ranch, or at an agricultural plant; second, they do not generate supplemental income for the agricultural enterprise. Practiced by people who are mainly from the middle or upper classes, it is opposed to *Urban Tourism*. It encloses *Agritourism*. It is also seen as a component of *Cultural Tourism* or *Ecotourism* (although the reciprocal is also valid).

7. *Village Tourism* is not defined anywhere, but the phrase appears in association with *Country Tourism*[19]

Conclusion: this study contributes to understand linguistic dimensions of agrotourism discourse, highlighting the role of lexical units in shaping cultural representations and marketing strategies. By analyzing agrotourism discourse in England and Uzbekistan, the research underscores the importance of considering linguistic factors in promoting rural tourism initiatives worldwide. Previous research has explored various aspects of agrotourism, including its economic, environmental, and socio-cultural implications. However, limited attention has been given to the linguistic aspects of agrotourism promotion, particularly in the context of different languages. Studies have shown that language choice and linguistic strategies can significantly influence tourists' perceptions and behaviors, highlighting the need for further investigation into this area.

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